

Deliverable D8.3

BY-COVID Long Term Sustainability Plan

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Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	All partners via workshop at GA		
Authors	Marieke Willems (ELIXIR) Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR) Peter Maccallum (ELIXIR) Maria Tyler (ELIXIR) All partners via workshop at GA		
Contributors	Corinne Martin (ELIXIR) Daniel Schmidtman (EMPIRICA) Romain David (ERINHA) Vasso Kalaitzi (KNAW-DANS) Simon Saldner (KNAW-DANS) Kostis Alexandrakis (EKKE) Markus Tuominen (TAU-FSD) Matti Heinonen (TAU-FSD)		
Acknowledgements (not grant participants)	[name surname (acronyms)]		
Reviewers	Henning Hermjakob (EMBL)		

Ilaria Colussi (BBMRI-ERIC)
Louiza Kalokairinou (ELIXIR)

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Executive Summary

During its 36 months, the BY-COVID project promoted and improved FAIR and open data sharing in support of European preparedness for COVID-19 and other infectious disease outbreaks. The BY-COVID results contribute to the outcomes envisaged in the HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-01 funding call.

This long term sustainability plan was built on the information collected through surveying the partners, and through face to face discussions of a selection of the BY-COVID assets for long term sustainability. The methodology applied in BY-COVID builds around a ‘data mobilisation’ pipeline - ‘Mobilise, Connect, Standardise, Expose & Analyse’. BY-COVID has developed, used and enhanced a set of re-usable and adoptable assets shown to support this.

Project Deliverables and outputs are all provided as open access material with permissive licensing. Where sensitive data has been processed, the results are the published anonymised and aggregated conclusions. We highlight illustrative use cases of BY-COVID assets, demonstrating their impact and wider adoption.

The sustainability of the outputs is embedded in the long term sustainability plan of the research infrastructures involved; as stable, mature entities they are well placed to host and maintain many of the assets adopted and enhanced via BY-COVID. Horizon Europe projects will play a significant future role in the development of Europe’s Pandemic Preparedness, and we have taken care to make sure the outputs of BY-COVID are visible to policy makers and can support the developing framework for European Pandemic Preparedness and mitigation of Antimicrobial Resistance. BY-COVID also contributed to the European Open Science Cloud and European Health Data Spaces; dedicated effort was made to contribute to the EOSC Implementation Roadmap, and the project as a whole is included as a societal impact demonstrator for EOSC and will inform the design of some aspects of the EHDS. BY-COVID and its outputs have been mentioned in European and international policy documents. We identify some of the blockers of and accelerators to sustainability across the different types of output.

In conclusion we recognise that the ESFRI Research Infrastructures’ core data services are a critical asset in support of pandemic preparedness; partnerships between agencies, researchers and e-infrastructure providers will be required to further develop and support a pathogen data analysis network; and that the interdisciplinary community of practice developed through the COVID-19 crisis should be supported through periods of

preparedness as well as response, in which the Research Infrastructures can play a key role.

Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective	Key Result No and description	Contributed
<p>Objective 1</p> <p>Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research.</p>	<p>1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures practice that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal.</p>	Yes
	<p>2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform.</p>	Yes
	<p>4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RI, national centres, policy makers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.</p>	Yes
<p>Objective 2</p> <p>Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres.</p>	<p>1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.</p>	Yes
	<p>2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.</p>	Yes
	<p>4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the on-going European VACCCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.</p>	Yes

Objective	Key Result No and description	Contributed
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19</p>	<p>1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility, and disease pathways.</p>	Yes
	<p>2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern</p>	<p>1. Broad uptake of viral <i>Data Hubs</i> across Europe deliver an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.</p>	Yes
	<p>2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision making.</p>	Yes
<p>Objective 5</p> <p>Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p>	Yes
	<p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.</p>	Yes
	<p>4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health</p>	Yes

Objective	Key Result No and description	Contributed
	sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.	

Table 1: Contribution to the project's objectives.

Background

As seen during the COVID-19 pandemic and other infectious disease outbreaks, research and clinical data and data analysis workflows need to be stored, shared, accessed, analysed, linked and processed across disciplines and national borders in a coordinated response. Such data can be generated and used by both researchers and healthcare professionals, and can include citizens' personal data.

The BY-COVID project

The BY-COVID project was funded by the European Union to make COVID-19 data accessible to scientists in research settings, but also to anyone who can use it, such as medical staff in hospitals or government officials to inform decision-making. The world has generated vast amounts of data in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, and continues to generate more. This data comes from many different sources, and identifying, connecting and integrating it for effective analysis and decision-making is challenging on many fronts.

During its 36 months, the BY-COVID project worked to implement its comprehensive, sustainable and evidence-informed plan to effectively promote and improve FAIR and open data sharing in support of European preparedness for COVID-19 and other infectious disease outbreaks. The BY-COVID work and results contribute to the Expected Outcomes as defined in the HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-01 funding call, and used as guiding principles for this long term sustainability plan:

- ***‘European researchers and public health actors fighting the spread of infectious diseases, e.g. COVID-19 and emerging infectious diseases are able to store, share, access, analyse, process and cite research and clinical data and other research digital objects across disciplines and national borders and to collaborate with global partners;***
- ***Federation of viral and human infectious disease data from national and international centres enables pan-European and global sharing and combination***

of research and clinical data, thereby catalysing and accelerating research advances to combat the COVID-19 pandemic and prepare for future outbreaks;

- ***Development of digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomic variations of SARS-CoV-2, linking genomic and clinical data to support timely identification of variants of concern, and subsequent rapid characterisation of such strains to inform public health action;***
- ***Linking of FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19, on other related viruses and diseases, and on socio-economic consequences, across research fields, from omics, clinical, and epidemiological research, to Social Sciences and Humanities accelerate infectious disease research, surveillance and outbreak investigation;***
- ***Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and to the development of the European Health Data Space (EHDS).¹***

ESFRI Research Infrastructures in BY-COVID

One of the strengths of the European research landscape is the programme of international research infrastructures which shape strategy and policy for research, represented by the members of the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI).

BY-COVID's consortium included ten ESFRI infrastructures with 'Landmark' status¹, and this provides a unique foundation for long term sustainability of the project's output - the research infrastructures are long established and have programmes which will remain in place after the end of the project to maintain services, skills, knowledge and ethical and legal compliance.

Table 2 below shows the ESFRI members and their Landmark dates. They are complemented by the European Molecular Biology Laboratory, which is an intergovernmental organisation which pre-dates the ESFRI and provides key services for data and hosting of some components of the ESFRI Infrastructures - Euro-Bioimaging, Instruct-ERIC and ELIXIR.

¹ ESFRI RI Portfolio - <https://ri-portfolio.esfri.eu/>

Research Infrastructure	Initiated	ESFRI Landmark
European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)	1974	(*)
Biobanks and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure (BBMRI)	2006	2016
Consortium of European Social Science Data Centres (CESSDA)	2006	2016
European Advanced Translational Research Infrastructure (EATRIS)	2006	2016
European Clinical Research Infrastructure (ECRIN)	2006	2016
ELIXIR	2006	2016
Infrafrontier	2006	2016
Instruct-ERIC	2006	2016
Euro-Bioimaging	2008	2018
European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents (ERINHA)	2008	2018
Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI)	2010	2021

Table 2: The maturity of the BY-COVID ESFRI Research Infrastructures. (*) EMBL is a member of EMBL is a member of the European Intergovernmental Research Organisation Forum (EIRO²).

Horizon Europe

The Horizon Europe funding programme has played a foundational role in the development of the research infrastructures, the research programmes and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), which together enabled BY-COVID and improved the wider response to COVID-19. In the ERAvsCorona Action Plan³ EU leaders committed to do everything possible to support research, to coordinate efforts and seek synergies within the European scientific and research community. BY-COVID has contributed to this vision and plan, via the identification and implementation of rapid response tools and services, thus delivering

² EIRO Forum - <https://www.eiroforum.org/>

³ ERAvsCorona Action Plan

https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-04/ec_rtd_era-vs-corona.pdf

a toolkit for pandemic preparedness. Specifically BY-COVID has contributed to improved Access to Research Infrastructures, connecting ESFRI landmarks and projects across disciplines and building synergies across EOSC and the European Health Data Space (EHDS), and delivering two comprehensive research data sharing platforms, the COVID-19 Data Platform and the Pathogens Portal.

Details of the ongoing connection to the Horizon Europe programme can be found in the *BY-COVID D6.1 Stakeholder engagement report*⁴, section 4.5.1.

The European Open Science Cloud

The European Open Science Cloud⁵ shares a vision with the partners in BY-COVID of a world of connected, Open and FAIR data. The BY-COVID project benefited directly from the pre-existing programme of work, with many of the partners already linked in projects such as EOSC-Life, a project to develop the EOSC in service of Life Science Infrastructures. Several of the products used to support the sharing and sustainability of pathogen analysis knowledge derived from EOSC projects (for example WorkflowHub and the RO-Crate format). As work continues to develop the vision of EOSC and the associated operating model, we can expect that the framework of EOSC will provide a cornerstone of the re-use of BY-COVID's knowledge and technology and will be an enabler of future pandemic preparedness and response.

The ongoing engagement with EOSC is described in the *BY-COVID D6.1 Stakeholder engagement report*, Section 4.5.2 'EOSC Association and the developing EOSC Partnership.'

Other Stakeholders

As defined in *BY-COVID D7.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy*⁶ the BY-COVID stakeholders can be categorised as:

- Data generators (e.g. deposition of FAIR data, data management) from the private and public sector
- Data consumers (e.g. data analysis, workflows) from the private and public sector
- Policy-makers and funding organisations
- Infrastructure providers
- National and international consortia and organisations involved in infectious disease research and allied social science research
- COVID-19 and infectious disease medical services and patient groups

⁴ BY-COVID D6.1 Stakeholder Engagement Report <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12820912>

⁵ The EOSC Association <https://eosc.eu/>

⁶ BY-COVID - D7.1 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884870>

- Adults, children and young people at risk of infectious diseases and affected by public health policy decisions

The sectors covered by the BY-COVID project include **social sciences, public health, molecular life sciences and medical sciences.**

Methods

Task 8.4 Development of long term sustainability plan for project outputs

This long term sustainability plan demonstrates how the results from the BY-COVID project contribute towards improving FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and open data sharing in support for European preparedness for COVID-19 and other infectious disease outbreaks.

This BY-COVID Long Term Sustainability Plan has been developed in the context of BY-COVID Task 8.4 *Development of long term sustainability plan for project outputs*, to ensure project impact is maximised including after the funded phase.

A first survey was conducted at month 17 to identify individual project outputs, assets and results. The survey was based on the format of EU reporting requirements for the project's midterm reporting. The following information was requested from project partners:

- Result type
- Technology Readiness Level
- Audience or target group
- Steps undertaken towards exploitation
- Market maturity
- Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)
- Licensing

Building on the information collected in the survey, at M25, during the General Assembly meeting in Barcelona⁷, project partners discussed a selection of the BY-COVID assets for long term sustainability. Blockers and accelerators for long term sustainability were identified, along with a roadmap with actions needed during and after the project lifetime, so as to contribute to maximising impact of the BY-COVID project's results.

BY-COVID Use Cases and Data Mobilisation as an Asset

The methodology applied in BY-COVID builds around the **Mobilise, Connect, Standardise, Expose & Analyse** pipeline as shown in the figure below. The overarching asset of the BY-COVID mobilisation pipeline is detailed in the Annex 1, with information about its target group and added value.

⁷ BY-COVID General Assembly 2023: <https://by-covid.org/events/by-covid-general-assembly-2023/> [accessed 02.11.2023]

Figure 1: BY-COVID data mobilisation pipeline data journey builds around three main pillars: Mobilise - Connect & expose data - Use & analyse.

The project mobilises existing data resources, by cataloguing and marshalling resources for research, and connecting and exposing the data and resources via the COVID-19 Data Portal. It has also driven use and analysis by connecting workflows, national portals and analysis environments such as Galaxy⁸. This proven interdisciplinary methodology is applicable to other scientific areas such as biodiversity and agriculture, which also benefit from integration with the humanities, social sciences and environmental sciences. The EOSC4Cancer project⁹, funded under HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-06 call, has adopted the same pipeline to deliver FAIR and open data sharing in support of cancer research. In addition, data from a number of ISIDORE pilot projects¹⁰ are being mobilised through the BY-COVID Data Mobilisation pipeline.

BY-COVID Assets

For the implementation of the **Mobilise, Connect, Standardise, Expose and Analyse pipeline**, BY-COVID has developed, used and enhanced a set of re-usable and adoptable

⁸ Galaxy: <https://usegalaxy.eu/> [accessed 02.11.2023]

⁹ EOSC4Cancer project: <https://eosc4cancer.eu/> [accessed 02.11.2023]

¹⁰ ISIDORE calls for pilot projects: <https://isidore-project.eu/calls/> [accessed 02.11.2023]

assets shown in the figure below, also accessible at the resources page on the project website¹¹.

Figure 2: BY-COVID selection of assets as published on the project dedicated webpage (as of end of 2023).

The BY-COVID consortium has investigated the sustainability of an initial set of 11 assets listed below and showcased on the resources page of the project website (Figure 2).

BY-COVID assets as published on the BY-COVID resources pages

[\[https://by-covid.org/resources/\]](https://by-covid.org/resources/) as of end of the project:

1. COVID-19 Data Portal
2. Pathogens Portal
3. SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs
4. Pathogen Data Hubs
5. Infectious Disease Toolkit
6. FAIRsharing.org
7. RO-Crate
8. WorkflowHub
9. COVID-19 Disease Map
10. BY-COVID Training Material
11. BY-COVID citizen engagement: An educational toolkit

In Annex 1 we describe all 11 individual BY-COVID assets and provide information on their target group and added value, type, access link, owner and dedicated branding. In the next section selection actions and impacts of the assets are described.

¹¹ BY-COVID dedicated webpage on project resources, or assets: <https://by-covid.org/resources/> [accessed 02.11.2023]

Results

In this section we provide an overview of the BY-COVID results supporting European pandemic preparedness, organised in three strands:

1. Project Deliverables and outputs;
2. Project assets in use, created or enhanced by the project to support FAIR and open data sharing across disciplines;
3. Engagement with Stakeholders raising awareness of the project, its assets and contributions to policy.

In the BY-COVID Long Term Sustainability Plan we use the term “assets”, instead of outputs and results as a number of the resources discussed are not developed solely by BY-COVID, they have separate ownership and BY-COVID have contributed to their further development. We address the sustainability for COVID specialisations, specifically more content and better features driven by BY-COVID.

Project Deliverables and outputs

BY-COVID provides open access to all its documentation via its Zenodo community¹². The main project website [<https://by-covid.org/>] will be sustained according to EC Horizon Europe rules and will provide an important point of access to:

1. BY-COVID deliverables¹³
2. BY-COVID resources & training¹⁴
3. BY-COVID publications¹⁵
4. BY-COVID citizen engagement material¹⁶

At month 36, the Zenodo community has 53 documents uploaded; the top 10 have been viewed between 417 and 3,193 times, and downloaded between 145 and 2,174 times.

¹² BY-COVID ZENODO community

<https://zenodo.org/communities/bycovid?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest> [accessed 14.11.2023]

¹³ BY-COVID outputs page <https://by-covid.org/outputs> [accessed 14.11.2023]

¹⁴ BY-COVID resources page <https://by-covid.org/resources> [accessed 14.11.2023]

¹⁵ BY-COVID outputs page <https://by-covid.org/outputs> [accessed 14.11.2023]

¹⁶ BY-COVID citizen engagement material <https://by-covid.org/usecases> [accessed 14.11.2023]

Project Assets in use

In this section we highlight illustrative use cases of BY-COVID assets, and provide quantitative information on their wider adoption.

Demonstrators in the Infectious Diseases Toolkit

The BY-COVID use cases demonstrate the usability and impact of connected data resources with clear metadata. Building on the mobilised and connected data collections and the solutions for national portals, incorporation into workflow analytics and traceability, the evolving demonstrator project prototyped research questions. The BY-COVID demonstrator is continuously enriched with new data, new evidence, and new hypotheses.

The demonstrators are outlined in Deliverables (D5.1 Enriched report viral variants and health outcomes, 5.2 Secondary use of vaccine trial data and biosamples, 5.3 Hot Spot detection, samples data collection and mechanistic analyses) and can be found in some detail in the Infectious Diseases Toolkit showcases¹⁷.

COVID-19 Data Platform & Pathogens Portal

A key exploitation of the COVID-19 Platform is the Pathogens Portal¹⁸. It aims to provide access to data and tools relating to pathogens, their human and animal hosts and their vectors. Current content spans bacterial, viral and eukaryotic parasite lineages alongside human host data. The Pathogens Portal builds on experience and software components of the COVID-19 Data Portal and develops them to address the challenge of pandemic preparedness.

¹⁷ IDTkit Showcase <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/>

¹⁸ Pathogens Portal : <https://www.pathogensportal.org/> [accessed 06.11.2023]

Figure 3: Pathogens Portal

CoVeO users, from the VEO project¹⁹, have made extensive use of the analysed data for their reports. To this date, 15 reports have been submitted to the European Commission. VEO Consortium members summarise mobilisation and analysis of SARS-CoV-2 sequence data submitted to the European COVID-19 Data Portal in the context of the VEO project, which aims to develop tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness²⁰.

Other use cases of the COVID-19 Data Portal:

- Metagenomic data on the Pathogens Portal
- DG SANTE asked for information on long covid, BY-COVID partners provided this information via the COVID-19 Data Portal
- CESSDA and EUI COVID-19 data onboarded to the COVID-19 Data Portal
- BY-COVID is collaborating with ISIDORE pilot projects to mobilise their data to the COVID-19 Data Portal.

SARS-CoV-2 data hubs & Pathogens data hubs

In the second year of the BY-COVID project, an open call was launched for proposals to support the implementation of additional SARS-CoV-2 data hubs and increase the flow of viral sequence data into the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), in line with open science principles.

¹⁹ VEO project: <https://www.veo-europe.eu/about-veo>

²⁰ VEO report 15:

<https://www.veo-europe.eu/news/nyhed?id=93b2c08e-3e20-48dc-90a4-d4b809a5f817>

Figure 4: BY-COVID Open Call for support for the implementation of SARS-CoV-2 data hubs

Other use cases are:

- The AMR Data Hub:
https://www.pathogensportal.org/datahubs/datahub/dcc_schubert
- An example of public SARS-CoV-2 Data Hub:
<https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search/sequences?crossReferencesOption=all&overrideDefaultDomain=true&db=sra-analysis-covid19&size=15>

BY-COVID Training

The BY-COVID project was an interdisciplinary effort that relied on an understanding of the data provided by its project partners. Training, capacity building, and outreach activities were essential in establishing a shared understanding among partners and ensuring the mobilisation of data both during and after the project's duration. Workshops, courses, hackathons and bridging events were organised. For a full list of these efforts see [D6.2](#), the Training efforts report.

FAIRsharing

A broad range of stakeholders come to FAIRsharing from across all research domains. A selection of official reports from funders and other organisations that recommend the use of FAIRsharing as a key asset for all stakeholders to enable FAIR data:

Funders

A selection of official reports from funders and other organisations that recommend the use of FAIRsharing as a key asset for all stakeholders to enable FAIR data:

"Horizon Europe Programme Guide" 2021 Funder: EU Horizon Europe - Funding Programme Discipline: All	"EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda" 2021 Funder: EU European Open Science Cloud - EOSC Discipline: All	"Recommendations on certifying services required to enable FAIR within EOSC" 2021 Funder: EU European Open Science Cloud - EOSC Discipline: All
"FAIR Metrics for EOSC" 2021 Funder: EU European Open Science Cloud - EOSC Discipline: All	"Six Recommendations for implementation of FAIR practice" 2020 Funder: EU European Open Science Cloud - EOSC Discipline: All	"Horizon 2020 projects working on COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2 and related topics" 2020 Funder: EU H2020 Discipline: Coronavirus research
"Horizon 2020 Annotated Grant Agreement" 2019 Funder: EU H2020 Discipline: All	"Sustainable and FAIR Data Sharing in the Humanities" 2020 Federation: Academies of Sciences and Humanities - ALLEA Discipline: Humanities	"Open Research Data and Data Management Plans" 2019 Funder: European Research Council - ERC Discipline: All
"Turning FAIR into Reality" 2018 Funder: EU European Open Science Cloud - EOSC Discipline: All	"Open Research Data Task Force Case Study" 2018 Governmental: UK Open Research Data Task Force Discipline: All	"Framework for Discipline-specific Research Data Management" 2018 Funders Association: Science Europe Discipline: All

Figure 5: FAIRsharing dedicated page on funder's recommendations for the use of FAIRsharing.

FAIRsharing has set up a dedicated community page²¹, to showcase its adopters, major funders, tools, communities etc, including the EOSC FAIR Metrics Task Force implementation method (<https://zenodo.org/record/7463421>).

WorkflowHub

The WorkflowHub is used and driven by 198 WorkflowHub Teams. It facilitates discovery and re-use of 430 workflows, and more specifically 45 covid tagged workflows with 7900+ downloads²².

The screenshot shows the WorkflowHub interface. At the top, there is a search bar with 'covid' entered and a 'Go' button. Below the search bar, there are filters for 'Created At' and 'Updated At', both set to 'Any time'. A sidebar on the left lists various tools and workflow types, such as 'fastp', 'MultiQC', 'BWA', 'SAMtools', 'MaBoSS', 'PhysiCell', 'Galaxy', and 'Nextflow'. The main content area displays a list of 57 workflows matching the criteria. The first workflow is 'covid-sequence-analysis-workflow' by David Yuan, created on 14th Nov 2023. The description of this workflow states: 'This is the official repository of the SARS-CoV-2 variant surveillance pipeline developed by Danish Technical University (DTU), Eotvos Lorand University (ELTE), EMBL-EBI, Erasmus Medical Center (EMC) under the Versatile Emerging Infectious Disease Observatory (VEO) project. The project consists of 20 European partners. It is funded by the European Commission.' The workflow has 17 views and 4 downloads.

Figure 6: Sample of COVID Workflows made accessible via WorkFlowhub to boost their reuse.

²¹FAIRsharing community page <https://fairsharing.org/communities>

²² <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/110>

RO-CRATE

RO-Crate is widely used and exposed to describe Data, Datasets and Workflows. Here we highlight the use of RO-Crate by the WorkflowHub.

WorkflowHub

WorkflowHub imports and exports Workflow RO-Crates, using it as an exchange format. They are a specialization of RO-Crate for packaging an executable workflow with all necessary documentation. It is aligned with, and intends to strictly extend, the more general Bioschemas ComputationalWorkflow profile.

Figure 7: RO-Crate use case at WorkflowHub

A dedicated page with 15+ use cases has been set in place on the RO-Crate website²³.

Socioeconomic data source integration methodology

Task 2.4 on relevant socioeconomic data sources has created a pipeline for getting metadata from the social sciences that are relevant for infectious diseases and, especially, COVID19, from data sources to the BY-COVID portal²⁴.

Socio-economic data sources are generally public and accessible, but authorisation or licensing agreements may be required to access some datasets. While the complete datasets may not always be openly available, the metadata usually is, and can be published along with the dataset description. Task 2.4 has identified relevant data sources for integration into the COVID19 portal. These data sources also offer programmatic access to their metadata using standards like the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH)²⁵. This enables the automated harvesting, harmonisation, and transformation of metadata into the OmicsDI²⁶ format, which can then be utilised by the COVID19 Data Portal. An advanced harvesting tool has been implemented with the use and extension of the open-source software DSpace²⁷ for the collection, processing, retrieving, searching, and browsing of the harvested metadata records. It can be customised to support different metadata schemes and different content providers. The basic protocol used for the harvesting process is OAI-PMH, which is supported by most repositories world-wide. This resource provides definitions of collections and communities. Using this resource, millions of metadata records can be aggregated. The metadata processes can be run periodically or triggered manually. Users can browse the harvested metadata records using keywords, topics or every other metadata field as well as query available metadata using advanced search functionalities.

²³ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/in-use/>

²⁴ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/data-sources/socioeconomic-data>

²⁵ <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

²⁶ <https://www.omicsdi.org/>

²⁷ <https://dspace.lyrasis.org/>

The search engine for the repository is the SOLR²⁸, a highly reliable, scalable and fault-tolerant search engine, that provides distributed indexing, replication and load-balanced querying, automated failover and recovery, centralised configuration and more. The harvesting tool has been extended with a set of endpoints that allow for the search and retrieval of the metadata records programmatically based on specific business needs, including the consumption of the metadata records to the COVID-19 Data Portal. The API is based on Open API principles²⁹ (RESTful) and provides JSON responses. The source code of the harvesting tool is currently hosted in a private repository in <https://gitlab.com/> but will be made publicly available in due course. XML transformation is done with a Python app (by-covid-xml-transformer) that uses the previously mentioned extended DSpace endpoints with query 'COVID' to get a list of records to harvest and link to where they can be harvested from. Those records are then harvested, processed (e.g. HTML tags removed) and transformed into extended OmicsDI format supported by the COVID-19 Data Portal. Transformation supports metadata that is in Dublin Core, DDI-Codebook 2.5³⁰ or DataCite³¹ format. The result is one XML file for every source.

Those files are validated against OmicsDI schema and also validated to be valid XML before being publicly available for the portal to retrieve and use. Developed software, tools, and pipeline should be made easy for anyone to set up. To accomplish this, Docker³² containers were chosen as the solution. Everything is “dockerized” and can be installed with one dockerfile. Configuration required is as minimal as possible. Comprehensive documentation has been or will be created for every required process in the pipeline, for both manual and automated processes.

Software used for XML transformation, SaxonC,³³ was made available from PyPI³⁴ during the project so it was changed to be installed from there to heavily simplify the installation.

Socioeconomic data integration into the COVID19 Data Portal

Socioeconomic data sources³⁵ described in D2.1 already integrated into the COVID19 Data Portal.³⁶ Task 2.4 has successfully integrated the CESSDA Data Catalogue,³⁷ and the EUI

²⁸ <https://solr.apache.org/>

²⁹ <https://www.openapis.org/what-is-openapi>

³⁰ <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Codebook/2.5/>

³¹ <https://schema.datacite.org/>

³² <https://www.docker.com/>

³³ <https://www.saxonica.com/saxon-c/index.xml>

³⁴ <https://pypi.org/project/saxonche/>

³⁵

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1SAHo6g8ION4uoUaKHsVOOVZhKyZjBm0K8MIBS5vSCBg/edit#gid=1196036810>

³⁶ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search/social-sciences>

³⁷ <https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/>

COVID19 Social Sciences data portal.³⁸ As described above, the Harvesting Tool will intermittently update metadata from these data sources. In addition, socioeconomic data from the Dutch National COVID-19 metadata portal³⁹ from HealthRI, which was added to the COVID19 Data Portal "Research Infrastructures" section by HealthRI, was made visible under the socioeconomics "Social sciences & humanities" section as well. T2.4 explored other potential data sources which were ultimately deemed unsuitable, as described in the BY-COVID T2.4 Sustainability Notes⁴⁰. The EUI COVID-19 SSH Data Portal, currently hosted and technically maintained by a contracted service provider, will be migrated in November 2024 to the permanent EUI internal infrastructure to ensure long term availability of the service as it stands.

Engagement with stakeholders

Throughout the project, BY-COVID has actively engaged with these stakeholders to raise awareness on the project and its assets for further uptake, figures from the first 18 months are illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 8: Dissemination actions during the first 18 months of the project, organised by stakeholder

³⁸ <https://covid19data.eui.eu/>

³⁹ <https://covid19initiatives.health-ri.nl/p/ProjectOverview>

⁴⁰

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1e3idjf7s36cWk0rYm8vkwOUFKy8lHZ8EdqRsVa5alcY/edit#heading=h.dnriir1jiwzm>

Discussion - Sustainability

For all BY-COVID assets, ongoing maintenance is vital to retain their status as useful pandemic preparedness resources. This has a financial cost, making it important to agree the necessary level of maintenance required especially for the BY-COVID developed assets and enhancements. To be sustainable, it is important to be able to accept new content after the project is over (e.g. reviewing pull requests/minimal editorial board).

Research Infrastructures as hosts of key Assets

The core mission of BY-COVID is to mobilise data from the domain infrastructures, connect and expose this data via the COVID-19 Data Portal and support analysis and reuse of data by the research community at large - ensuring that this analysis can link to emerging variants via VEO. The project brings together central hubs, data coordinating centres and national partners of the relevant life science RI (BBMRI, EATRIS, ECRIN, ELIXIR, EU-OpenScreen, EuroBioImaging, ERINHA, INSTRUCT, MIRRI), social science RI (CESSDA + partners, EU), and public health (PHIRI + national public health partners).

This sustainability plan is therefore embedded in the long term sustainability plan of the research infrastructures involved, maintaining the assets adopted and enhanced via BY-COVID. The ELIXIR long term sustainability plan is a valuable example, as a number of the BY-COVID assets discussed are among the 400 services run by ELIXIR Nodes⁴¹.

In addition, BY-COVID builds on and actively contributed to the *Recommendations for FAIR Resources in Life Sciences research: EOSC-Life's Lessons*^{42 43}.

Horizon Europe projects and the development of Europe's Pandemic Preparedness

BY-COVID adopted and contributed to a number of European Commission funded tools and services. These tools and services are owned and maintained by their previous owners and communities, partnering in BY-COVID. We have showcased them in the infographic below.

⁴¹ Smith A, Martin C and ELIXIR Partners. ELIXIR's long term sustainability plan (2023) [version 1; not peer reviewed]. F1000Research 2023, 12(ELIXIR):534 (document) (<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119412.1>)

⁴² David, R., Rybina, A., Burel, J.-M., Heriche, J.-K., Audergon, P., Boiten, J.-W., Coppens, F., Crockett, S., Exter Katrina, Fahrener, S., Fratelli, M., Goble, C., Gormanns, P., Grantner, T., Gruning, B., Gurwitz, K. T., Hancock, J., Harmse, H., Holub, P., ... Gribbon, P. (2023). Preprint: "Be Sustainable", Recommendations for FAIR Resources in Life Sciences research: EOSC-Life's Lessons. In EMBO Journal (6.3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8338931>

⁴³ "Be sustainable": EOSC-Life recommendations for implementation of FAIR principles in life science data handling <https://doi.org/10.15252/embj.2023115008>

Figure 9: BY-COVID assets and their funding streams

When looking at the long term sustainability of BY-COVID funded assets we identify **assets co-funded with other initiatives**, and **assets primarily funded by BY-COVID**.

The following projects have been identified and contacted to foster the wider adoption of BY-COVID assets:

project/ initiative	Outcome of synergy
EOSC-Life	EOSC-Life outcomes formed foundation for BY-COVID work (e.g. RO-Crate, WorkFlowHub, etc); EOSC-Life funded specific functionalities of COVID-19 Data Platform
ISIDORe	ISIDORe funded projects will use the services and practices developed under BY-COVID to mobilise their data for re-use.
VEO	VEO consortium members contributed to the development of the COVID-19 Portal and promoted the mobilisation of raw datasets.
ReCoDID	Collaboration agreement with REACT, ReCoDID & BY-COVID for data mobilisation towards COVID-19 Data Platform.
REACT	Collaboration agreement with REACT, ReCoDID & BY-COVID for data mobilisation towards COVID-19 Data Platform.
ELIXIR-CONVERGE	The CONVERGE funded network of ELIXIR SARS-CoV-2 data brokering platforms to strengthen and connect national capacity towards the International Pathogen Surveillance Network, now funded under NIH NIAID Bioinformatics Resource Centres

	programme.
SSHOC	Social Science data mobilisation towards COVID-19 Data Platform. SSH community taking part in the BY-COVID training events and future uptake of the BY-COVID training materials.
GDI	Evaluating adoption of the IDToolkit to promote knowledge sharing in pathogen-host studies including human genomics.
EOSC4Cancer	Data mobilisation approach adopted for Cancer data sets.
COUNTERACT	<p>Targeted sharing of the following results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Umbrella Data Management Plans to integrate FAIR data: lessons from the ISIDORE and BY-COVID consortia for pandemic preparedness https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520086 • D2.1 Initial data and metadata harmonisation at domain level to enable fast responses to COVID-19 https://zenodo.org/record/7017728 • D2.2 Data Access and Transfer across research domains and jurisdictions https://zenodo.org/record/8101848 • D3.1 Metadata standards https://zenodo.org/record/6885016 • D3.2 Implementation of cloud-based, high performance, scalable indexing system https://zenodo.org/record/7129553 • IDToolkit https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/ and more information on how to contribute: https://by-covid.org/news/infectious-diseases-toolkit/
EVORA	Ongoing integration of data sources and catalogues with the Pathogens portal; adoption of recommended practices; contribution to the IDTkit.
EVOLVE	Continued development of Data Steward roles for data mobilisation initiated under BY-COVID.
ELIXIR-STEERS	Continued development of Data Stewardship skills for data mobilisation in nodes; international outreach and connections to organisations beyond Europe.

Table 3: Relations with selected programmes and projects

Stakeholder roles in Data for Pandemic Preparedness

BY-COVID supporting European Pandemic Preparedness

In April 2020, EU leaders committed to do everything possible to support research, to coordinate efforts and seek synergies within the European scientific and research community in the **ERAvsCorona Action Plan**⁴⁴. BY-COVID has contributed to the swift implementation of the plan, providing a toolkit for pandemic preparedness, specifically focusing on two of its actions:

1. **Access to Research Infrastructures**, connecting 10 ESFRI landmarks and projects from molecular biology via clinical data to social sciences, identifying and implementing rapid response tools and services delivering a toolkit for pandemic preparedness.
2. **Research data sharing platform**, via its work on the COVID-19 Data Platform to enable the rapid collection and sharing of available research data. A joint effort by the European Commission, the European Bioinformatics Institute of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL-EBI), the ELIXIR infrastructure and the EOSC-Life, ELIXIR-CONVERGE, VEO and RECODID H2020 projects, as well as the EU Member States and other partners.

Furthermore, BY-COVID aligns with the **One Health** approach building on the latest technological advances, exploiting and contributing to the European Open Science Cloud capabilities for data access and federation as well as relevant standards and policies for managing, sharing and reusing research data. BY-COVID joined forces with the ISIDORE project (funded under the emergency call HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02), *Accelerating research infrastructure services for rapid research responses to COVID-19 and other infectious disease epidemics*. By expanding the resources made available to users and their access to cutting-edge services, the ISIDORE project intends to demonstrate that a dedicated integrated epidemic disease research infrastructure service can significantly impact the infectious diseases research landscape, and should ultimately become a permanent capacity embedded in the EU's overarching strategy for pandemic preparedness and crisis management. BY-COVID and ISIDORE share a number of partner Research Infrastructures (RIs), making the dataflows from ISIDORE Transnational Access projects into COVID-19 Data Portal a reality. In addition, the collaboration resulted in the *Umbrella Data Management Plans to integrate FAIR data: lessons from the ISIDORE and BY-COVID consortia for pandemic preparedness*⁴⁵.

⁴⁴ ERAvsCorona Action Plan

https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-04/ec_rtd_era-vs-corona.pdf

⁴⁵ David, R., Richard, A. S., Connellan, C., Lauer, K. B., Chiusano, M. L., Goble, C., Houde, M., Kemmer, I., Keppler, A., Lieutaud, P., Ohmann, C., Panagiotopoulou, M., Raza Khan, S., Rybina, A., Soiland-Reyes, S., Wit, C., Wittner, R., Andrade Buono, R., Marsh, S. A., ... Ewbank, J. (2023).

BY-COVID contributing to the European Open Science Cloud and European Health Data Spaces

BY-COVID Contributes to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS) in the dedicated task 6.2. As of writing, the project has already contributed via;

- Exchange of technical “know-how” on surveillance systems for pathogens, so that countries can more efficiently progress in their journeys toward operational and resilient infrastructures for preparedness (WP6).
- Communication channels (new or strengthened) so that research infrastructures can convey EOSC-related input to the EOSC Partnership as it is being built, notably through the EOSC Association and other EOSC-related projects (WP6).
- Engagement and synergies with projects such as TEHDAS, which are contributing to the building of the EHDS (WP6).
- Engagement with policy-makers in intergovernmental organisations, funders, and research publishers, to shape the policy landscape and amplify the impact of the project, given their role in shaping research practices and in forward planning towards preparedness (WP6).
- Twenty training events (with over 70 training materials), hackathons and ‘contentathons’ were organised in collaboration with experts from WP1-WP5, gathering hundreds of BY-COVID partners, users and data providers. These training and exchange events enabled national centres to build capacity, train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and exchange experiences and knowledge. (WP6)

Dedicated effort was made to contribute to the EOSC Implementation Roadmap⁴⁶, where the project as a whole is included as a societal impact demonstrator for EOSC. BY-COVID provides a demonstrator on how EOSC and EOSC technologies, workflows, principles, and standards can be shaped to respond to the needs of transnational access users and of large user groups. It will also demonstrate how EOSC can deliver against the societal and policy challenges defined by Horizon Europe and the EC. In addition, a number of BY-COVID assets are included on the Roadmap.

Umbrella Data Management Plans to integrate FAIR data : lessons from the ISIDORE and BY-COVID consortia for pandemic preparedness. In Data Science Journal (Number Data Management Planning across Disciplines and Infrastructures). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7998443>

⁴⁶ EOSC Roadmap: <https://eosc.eu/roadmap/> [accessed 02.11.2023]

BY-COVID contributing to policy making towards pandemic preparedness

BY-COVID published a dedicated Policy Brief⁴⁷, presenting its preliminary results in the context of the project's comprehensive, sustainable and evidence-informed plan to effectively promote and improve FAIR and open data sharing in support for European preparedness for COVID-19 and other infectious disease outbreaks. The Brief also places the project and its results in the context of the EOSC Partnership, the development of the EHDS and HERA. In addition, BY-COVID and its outputs have been mentioned in 14 European and international policy documents, from bodies such as the European Commission, Swedish Presidency of the Council of the European Union, United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI), World Health Organisation (WHO), Wellcome Trust and The Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy Committee (BEIS) for the G7 Open Science Working Group, a sample is shown the figure below, for a full list of these documents see *D6.1 Stakeholder engagement report*⁴⁸.

Figure 10: BY-COVID and its outputs were mentioned in a range of policy documents

⁴⁷ Niklas Blomberg, Marieke Willems, Corinne S. Martin, Andy Smith, Elaine Harrison, Jose-Maria Carazo, Enrique Bernal-Delgado, Iris van Dam, Romain David, Patricia M. Palagi, & Martina Draščić Capar. (2023). Open data to support European pandemic preparedness. (1.1). Zenodo.

⁴⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7950479>

⁴⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/12820912>

Blockers and Accelerators

BY-COVID assets share the same sustainability blockers and accelerators, but issues and strategies for long term sustainability vary based on the nature of the service or product and whether it is specialised for pathogens research or also serves a wider community.

Topic	Blockers	Accelerators
People	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retentions of skills and abilities; institutional knowledge and continuation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing and developed skills and abilities • Developed collaborations (networks & communities) through the various projects that have supported the Data Hubs
Interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incomplete adoption of the FAIR implementation profile; same datasets with different IDs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being able to filter data from hubs that are private • Interconnectivity of data hubs nationally
Organisational Ownership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dependencies on other resources - for example Wikidata, Reactome, FAIRDOMHub 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure of the portal provided by EMBL-EBI • Built both portals on existing infrastructure, formats, frameworks and feeds. • Several services (WorkflowHub, Galaxy) are ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resources • BY-COVID accompanying technologies (FAIRDOMHub, Galaxy, WorkflowHub, RO-Crate) established in ELIXIR and EOSC
Funding and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overhead of aligning multiple resources • Fadeout of COVID-19 funding interest, community-based effort 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OSCARS cascade funding for projects supporting Open Science practices • National funding frameworks, such as BioFAIR (UK) • Upcoming granted projects: EVERSE, EVORA, EOSC-ENTRUST • Having a critical mass of content to help justify further investment
Uptake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data contributions • Keeping content updated and curated • No clear incentives for voluntary contribution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All lessons learned (knowledge and outputs) during the COVID-19 pandemics by the BY-COVID partners should end up in IDTKit during the project. • Collaboration with other initiatives (One Health, Pandemic Preparedness)

Topic	Blockers	Accelerators
	E.g. credit for reviewing activities	Partnership) that cover similar data on a strategic level. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usefulness of “specialty” portals, like COVID-19 Data Portal, which help ensure reach-out to specific user communities and higher impact and data-reuse. • Adopt as a use case in capacity building initiatives, in EOSC and EHDS, for example.

Table 4: Blockers and enablers of sustainability

A sustainability Roadmap for European Pathogen Data

BY-COVID was founded in the midst of Europe’s pandemic response, and has shaped the role of Open Data in planning for future pandemic preparedness.

In the area of funding directed to pathogens and public health, the project benefited from programmes such as VEO and PHIRI and the set-up of HERA in 2021. The ISIDORE and EVORA projects continue to support pathogen preparedness research and resources which will be needed in future response; and in parallel the BE-READY and DESIGN OH AMR projects have produced Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas with data at their heart.

The project also leveraged its position in the EOSC and ESFRI landscape, taking as input technologies developed under EOSC-Life and ELIXIR CONVERGE, and the services developed over many years by the ESFRI Research Infrastructures; the Research Infrastructures will persist after the end of the project and will provide a long term hosting solution for many of the components and some of the knowledge and people networks built through the project.

Figure 11 lays out the timeline of these initiatives and shows how there are several routes to sustainability based on uptake by specific funding instruments supported by ongoing infrastructure investments.

Figure 11: BY-COVID Sustainability Roadmap. BY-COVID fits into a landscape of Pathogens and Public Health projects - VEO, PHIRI and the foundation of HERA before the start, ISIDORe started in parallel, and the DESIGN OH-AMR, BE-READY and EVORA and their follow on programmes as present and future beneficiaries of the services and approaches developed. It also benefited from the ESFRI and EOSC frameworks - ELIXIR-CONVERGE and EOSC-Life produced outputs which were used in BY-COVID, EVOLVE and ELIXIR-STEERS will continue to develop the services and Data Stewardship communities. All of the services, knowledge and networks were developed together with long-founded ESFRI infrastructures and will form parts of their portfolios after the end of the project.

Conclusions

From the development of BY-COVID and the evaluation of the future of its services, we can make three statements about likely routes to sustainability, around the importance of core data services, an opportunity for e-Infrastructures and EOSC to contribute, and the role of the Research Infrastructures in maintaining a pathogens community of practice.

The ESFRI Research Infrastructures' core data services are a critical asset in support of pandemic preparedness.

The Pathogens Portal represents a synthesis of lessons learned from the COVID-19 portal; while we expect that disease-specific portals will form a component of emergency response in the future, we will encourage all of our partners and stakeholders to see the Pathogens Portal as the focus of their 'non-emergency' data preparedness to ensure that there is a common pool of expertise and knowledge and a baseline of common knowledge on all diseases of pandemic potential.

Partnerships between agencies, researchers and e-infrastructure providers could support a pathogen data analysis network.

The Pathogen Data Hubs approach has already demonstrated its utility; we will seek to partner with e-Infrastructure providers and developments in the European Data Spaces (including EOSC) to continue to develop this approach as a technological component of the overall solution. The NIH have already announced funding for an international Pathogen Data Network⁴⁹; we will seek to develop and support the European contribution to this network.

The BY-COVID services are well positioned to support the SRIA of PPP and OH-AMR and our members will seek to develop and promote the BY-COVID services as solutions to the data mobilisation and analysis problems in this area.

The interdisciplinary community of practice developed through the COVID-19 crisis should be supported through periods of preparedness as well as response.

⁴⁹ NIH/NIAID Pathogen Data Network <https://pathogendatanetwork.org/>

The network of RI partners has developed expertise and ways of working through the COVID-19 pandemic and the BY-COVID project; we will keep this on the agenda of cross-RI meetings. The IDTkit will continue as a shared endeavour across the RIs and a focus for Communities of practice (for example the new ELIXIR Pathogen Data Focus Group⁵⁰).

⁵⁰ ELIXIR Pathogen Data Focus Group <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/pathogen-data>

Annex 1 - BY-COVID Assets

In this annex we list all BY-COVID assets, exploited via BY-COVID and suitable for long term sustainability after the end of the project lifetime in September 2024.

BY-COVID Mobilise, Connect, Standardise, Expose and Analyse pipeline

<p><i>Branding</i></p>	
<p><i>Description</i></p>	<p>BY-COVID Mobilise, Connect, Standardise, Expose and Analyse pipeline</p> <p>Mobilise data. The ecosystem of data affiliated with an infectious disease outbreak is vast, ranging from social sciences, to public health, and biomolecular data. Dataset discovery remains a significant challenge. Not all data can be shared freely and immediately, consideration needs to be given to privacy of access controlled patient data, accreditation of data providers and national legislation amongst many others⁵¹. BY-COVID allows mobilisation - meaning access and transfer - of data by using a trialled system of SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs⁵² and other existing infrastructures, following community practised standards and delegating ultimate data responsibility to the data providers. The consortium includes a critical mass of data resources across domains (scientific, medical, public health and policy), that by the end of BY-COVID will be mobilised and connected⁵³.</p> <p>Connect & expose data. Exposing and effective connection and linking of different data types requires indexing. Indexing and</p>

⁵¹ Cortada, A. J., Gormanns, P., Furlani, A., Van Dam, I., Portell-Silva, L., Belien, J., David, R., Navest, R., Heinonen, M., Tuominen, M., Kondyli, D., Freeberg, M., Capella-Gutierrez, S., Mathur, A., Kleemola, M., Colussi, I., Giuffre, C., & Blomberg, N. (2023). BY-COVID D2.2: Data Access and Transfer across research domains and jurisdictions. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8101848>

⁵² [link to D1.2 Preparedness Data Hub]

⁵³ Giles, T., Quinlan, P., Belien, J., Lischke, J., Portell-Silva, L., Capella-Gutierrez, S., Karki, R., Kalaitzi, V., Bernal-Delgado, E., & Keppler, A. (2022). BY-COVID- D2.1 - Initial data and metadata harmonisation at domain level to enable fast responses to COVID-19 (V1.0). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7017728>

	<p>incorporation into the COVID-19 Data Portal proceeds via a flexible, tiered system for data integration.⁵⁴ BY-COVID consolidated the technical basis for the tiered integration, set out the requirements for interoperability of data (best practices, community endorsed standards, harmonisation and management of meta-data, sample identifiers/persistent identifiers, vocabularies) and support integration of COVID-19 data resources into the COVID-19 Data Portal⁵⁵.</p> <p>Use & analyse data. BY-COVID provides standardised data management and analysis methods and protocols to ensure FAIR is an integral part of the data creation process and all data is integrated in existing infrastructures. BY-COVID compiles reproducible and open access analysis methods and protocols and makes them openly available to all researchers. Trustworthiness is paramount for data publishing in pandemics, BY-COVID has dedicated tasks on quality and traceability (provenance), a key element for trustable AI and machine learning applications.</p>
<i>Target Group</i>	Data Managers & Stewards, Researchers, Public Health agencies, Industry, business partners, EU Institutions and/or agencies, End users (practitioners, farmers, etc), Research Infrastructures
<i>Added value</i>	Quality data from a range of sources is connected and made available for research use and policy formulation. The efficiency of mobilisation has the potential to influence the timeliness of information and shape health and social interventions during outbreaks.
<i>Type of result</i>	PRODUCT

⁵⁴ Hermjakob, H., Kleemola, M., Moilanen, K., Tuominen, M., Sansone, S.-A., Lister, A., David, R., Panagiotopoulou, M., Ohmann, C., Belien, J., Lischke, J., Juty, N., & Soiland-Reyes, S. (2022). BY-COVID D3.2: Implementation of cloud-based, high performance, scalable indexing system. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7129553>

⁵⁵ Hermjakob, H., Kleemola, M., Ventouratou, M., Lister, A., Sansone, S.-A., David, R., Lischke, J., Navest, R., Belien, J., Juty, N., Soiland-Reyes, S., & Goble, C. (2023). BY-COVID D3.3.1: COVID-19 Data Portal. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8386828>

<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	Published in Deliverables, papers and pre-prints. Showcased on Infectious Diseases Toolkit Adopted in EOSC4CANCER, ISIDORe, EVORA projects
<i>Owner</i>	Research Infrastructures and EMBL - through IDTkit editorial board.
<i>Access/Link</i>	https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/

COVID-19 Data Portal

<i>Branding</i>	
<i>Short description</i>	The COVID-19 Data Portal is one of the three components of the European COVID-19 Data Platform: Data Hubs, FEAGA and the COVID-19 Data Portal. The Data Portal brings together and continuously updates the relevant COVID-19 datasets and tools. It is a critical resource that provides access to literature and data on both the SARS-CoV-2 virus and the disease.
<i>Target Group</i>	Researchers, Public Health agencies, Industry, business partners, EU Institutions and/or agencies, Policy makers and authorities, international , Policy makers and authorities, national, End users (practitioners, farmers, etc), Research Infrastructures
<i>Added value</i>	Making a range of infectious disease data sources widely discoverable, accessible and interoperable is important for research and innovation, which is increasingly multidisciplinary in nature. Multidisciplinary data is also critical for public health decision-making, where policy questions are complex and evidence from biomolecular research, clinical studies and social sciences must be taken into account. Solutions for COVID-19 can be extended to other pathogens.
<i>Type of result</i>	SERV – Service (Improved)
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	Prototyping in production environment, Contribution to standards
<i>Owner</i>	The portal is hosted by EMBL-EBI, open (meta)data are provided by the sources
<i>Access/Link</i>	https://www.covid19dataportal.org/

SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs

<i>Branding</i>	Accessed through:
<i>Short description</i>	<p>The SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs form one of the three components of the European COVID-19 Data Platform (Data Hubs, FEAGA and the COVID-19 Data Portal), and consist of: submission services, analysis infrastructure & workflows, presentation services & tools, and visualisation services. Viral sequence data generated from the outbreak at national or regional levels can be submitted to the SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs via a variety of upload tools and be systematically analysed. Essential metadata, such as sampling tracking identifiers, sampling time, geographical location, method of sampling, health status of host and sequencing platform/strategy, are captured alongside sequence data. SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs further offer visualisation and phylogenetic analysis tools.</p>
<i>Target Group</i>	Public health agencies, Research laboratories, Reference laboratories
<i>Added value</i>	<p>Increased mobilisation of openly shared SARS-CoV-2 sequence data to support surveillance and analysis. This can contribute towards an improved understanding of the dynamics of the virus spread, its evolution and virus-host interactions. Compared to other repositories, the SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs have the advantage of capturing raw sequence data which enables reproducibility of analysis results.</p>
<i>Type of result</i>	SERV – Service, (New)
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	Used as the basis for Pathogen Data Hubs

<i>Owner</i>	The technology builds upon existing EMBL-EBI infrastructure; Tools (analysis, visualisation and phylogeny) were developed as part of the Horizon 2022 project VEO and integrated into EMBL-EBI; Sequencing data and metadata are provided by national or international organisations.
<i>Access/Link</i>	https://www.covid19dataportal.org/data-hubs

Pathogens Portal

<i>Branding</i>	<h1 data-bbox="718 302 1388 403">PATHOGENS</h1> <p data-bbox="718 403 1388 448">Surveillance Identification Investigation</p>
<i>Short description</i>	<p>The Pathogens Portal builds on experience and software components of the COVID-19 Data Portal and develops them to address the challenge of pandemic preparedness. It provides an entry point for the Pathogen Data Hubs, a specific Outbreak page monitoring priority pathogens, and a central discovery platform for literature, datasets and tools related to a broad range of pathogens.</p>
<i>Target Group</i>	<p>Researchers, Public Health agencies, Industry, business partners, EU Institutions and/or agencies, Policy makers and authorities, international , Policy makers and authorities, national, End users (practitioners, farmers, etc), Research Infrastructures</p>
<i>Added value</i>	<p>Making a range of infectious disease data sources widely discoverable, accessible and interoperable is important for research and innovation, which is increasingly multidisciplinary in nature. Multidisciplinary data is also critical for public health decision-making, where policy questions are complex and evidence from biomolecular research, clinical studies and social sciences must be taken into account. Solutions for COVID-19 can be extended to other pathogens.</p>
<i>Type of result</i>	<p>SERV – Service, (new)</p>
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	<p>Prototyping in production environment, Contribution to standards. Component of NIH/NIAID Pathogen Data Network.</p>
<i>Owner</i>	<p>The portal is hosted by EMBL-EBI, open (meta)data are provided by the sources</p>

<i>Access/Link</i>	https://www.pathogensportal.org/
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Pathogen Data hubs

<i>Branding</i>	Falls under: <h1>PATHOGENS</h1> <p>Surveillance Identification Investigation</p>
<i>Short description</i>	<p>The Pathogen Data Hubs include ongoing development to generate a set of tools that includes: workflows for sequence data upload, structured storage and sharing of sequences and accompanied contextual metadata, as well as data analysis interpretations. While SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs are tailored to capture viral sequence data generated from the COVID-19 outbreak and continuous monitoring of spread at national and regional levels, the Pathogen Data Hubs will aim to serve a wider range of pathogens, including bacterial, fungal or parasites (with currently limited functionalities for analysis beyond viruses and bacteria).</p>
<i>Target Group</i>	<p>Public health agencies, Research laboratories, Reference laboratories</p>
<i>Added value</i>	<p>Areas of public and animal health as well as food safety would benefit from rapid data sharing and analysis when it comes to emergencies, as demonstrated during the COVID-19 pandemic. Providing an infrastructure for data sharing in structured formats that would allow for integration of repurposed tools that could be extended to other pathogens, or for a flexible implementation of new tools, would offer an increased incentive for data sharing.</p>
<i>Type of result</i>	<p>SERV – Service, (new)</p>
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	<p>Component of NIH/NIAID Pathogen Data Network.</p>

<i>Owner</i>	The technology builds upon existing EMBL-EBI infrastructure; The initial concept and tools (analysis, visualisation) were developed as part of the Horizon 2022 projects COMPARE and VEO and integrated into EMBL-EBI; Sequencing data and metadata are provided by national or international organisations.
<i>Access/Link</i>	https://www.pathogensportal.org/datahubs

Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk)

<i>Branding</i>	Infectious Diseases Toolkit
<i>Short description</i>	The IDTk is a platform for knowledge exchange to enable data mobilisation, connection & exposure, and use & analysis. It aims to provide a compilation of past and present efforts, collect country specific strategies, and contextualised best practices from previous responses.
<i>Target Group</i>	Researchers, Research Infrastructures, EU Institutions and/or agencies, International, national and regional policy makers and authorities.
<i>Added value</i>	Knowledge exchange platform with example solutions, and best practices to be applied or enhanced to tackle data challenges affecting the response to infectious diseases outbreaks. IDTk strives to keep content accessible, keeping the text simple, highlighting the challenges to be tackled and linking out to deeper and specialised resources. IDTk also offers a platform for groups to showcase their developments and solutions, reducing duplication of efforts and encouraging adoption of existing solutions.
<i>Type of result</i>	PROD – Product (new)
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	The resource is publicly available, and encourages contributions. Community and content building events such as Contentathons ⁵⁶ are a source of knowledge, but also serve as dissemination activities.
<i>Owner</i>	Tartu University (ELIXIR-EE) / VIB (ELIXIR-BE) have been leading the task and deployment. Content managed by the Editorial Board.

⁵⁶ IDTk contentathon:

<https://by-covid.org/news-events/infectious-diseases-toolkit-idtk-contentathon-event/> [accessed 19.10.2023]

Access/Link

<https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/>

FAIRsharing.org

<i>Branding</i>	
<i>Short description</i>	<p>A curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies. FAIRsharing enacts the FAIR Principles by promoting the value and the use of these resources, which are essential pillars of the research life cycle.</p>
<i>Target Group</i>	<p>Researchers, Developers & Curators, Journal Publishers, Librarian & Trainers, Funders, Society & Alliances</p>
<i>Added value</i>	<p>Providing curated descriptions and network graphs of the relationships among (meta)data standards, the databases that implement them, and the policies that recommend them, FAIRsharing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Guides consumers to discover, select and use these resources with confidence. ● Helps producers to make their resources more visible, more widely adopted and cited. ● Provides humans and tools with access to trustworthy content to enable data management tasks.
<i>Type of result</i>	<p>SERV, service (Improved) - TRL 9</p>
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	<p>FAIRsharing is already adopted and used by publishers, funders (incl EU policies, as well EOSC policies, Task Forces and projects), and tools (https://fairsharing.org/communities), and it is an endorsed output of the Research Data Alliance, and a recommended resource of ELIXIR, embedded in the current and new strategic plan. The FAIRsharing Community Champions brings together community of domain and discipline experts to contribute (https://fairsharing.org/community_champions) and build Educational material (https://fairsharing.org/educational)</p>

<i>Owner</i>	University of Oxford, ELIXIR-UK Node. Contribution from a large community, beside ELIXIR, since FAIRsharing covers all disciplines.
<i>Access/Link</i>	https://fairsharing.org

WorkflowHub

<i>Branding</i>	
<i>Short description</i>	<p>A FAIR workflow registry that provides a single access point for the findability and accessibility of workflows, indexed and linked to the workflows native repositories. Workflows are registered using a metadata framework for interoperability and reusability developed by the EOSC-Life project, using Bioschemas and RO-Crate, and adopted by Galaxy and Nextflow. All BY-COVID workflows should be registered in the WorkflowHub. 18+ workflow systems are represented in WorkflowHub to date. Workflow developers can organise themselves into Teams of communities of practice and for enclave sharing as well as publishing workflows publicly with DOIs. WorkflowHub adheres to the 9 best practices of Scicodes.net and is an early implementer of FAIR Signposting, as promoted by FAIR-IMPACT. GA4GH API compliant.</p>
<i>Target Group</i>	<p>Researchers, Developers & Curators, Journal Publishers, Librarian & Trainers, Funders, Society & Alliances</p>
<i>Added value</i>	<p>Single access point for the findability and accessibility of workflows by researchers and other workflow developers supporting existing workflow platform repos. Integration with LifeMonitor and other services and workflow managers to support smooth registration and added value services for testing, curating and launching workflows; Analytics to support contributors and Teams bring together CoP; Workflow registry for funders and publishers to showcase workflows funded and workflows associated with publications; also supports SOPs registration (few (any?) public open source SOP registry currently available). Other companion objects with workflows supported and packages using RO-Crate for exchange.</p>

<i>Type of result</i>	SERV, service (Improved)
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	WorkflowHub exited beta in Sep 2021 and since then Workflow registrations have doubled year on year. The Hub is used by 20+ EU projects/ consortia and the Australian BioCommons (who provide the product owner). A basket of projects fund the core development and a WorkflowHub Club coordinates community outreach and developments. WorkflowHub is known by the workflow community (https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1011369 Sept 2023 cites it for example). Discussions are underway with journals for the Hub to be a recognised registry. WorkflowHub is registered as an EOSC Service (EOSC Portal) and an ELIXIR Service.
<i>Owner</i>	Main development and hosting at University of Manchester. (ELIXIR-UK) But with many other partners, benefits from a large community .
<i>Access/Link</i>	https://workflowhub.eu/ https://workflowhub.org

RO-Crate

<i>Branding</i>	
<i>Short description</i>	<p>RO-Crate is a community-developed standardised approach for research output packaging with rich metadata. Lightweight way of packaging data (data can be anything, such as software or workflow) and its metadata. Mixed RO-Crates bundle different kinds of objects. Used for reporting, archiving, citing, exchanging between repositories, registries and services and reproducibility. When combined with FAIR signposting (FSP) a powerful implementation of FAIR Digital Objects as proposed by the FDO Forum.</p>
<i>Target Group</i>	<p>Researchers, Developers & Curators, Journal Publishers, Librarian & Trainers, Funders, Society & Alliances. Primarily middleware so really aimed at developers and service providers who delivery to other suppliers.</p>
<i>Added value</i>	<p>Arguably the only reference implementation framework for FAIR Digital Objects. Standardised mechanism for reporting, archiving, citing, exchanging objects (data, workflows, mixed) between repositories, registries and services with an extensible metadata framework that uses off the shelf web technology. Used as the Workflow exchange and archiving packaging by WorkflowHub, LifeMonitor and support developed by Galaxy and being explored for Nextflow.</p>
<i>Type of result</i>	<p>PRODUCT (Improved)</p>
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	<p>Used by workflow collaboratory developed by EOSC-Life cluster & BY-COVID for workflow packaging (Workflow RO-Crate), workflow provenance (Workflow Run RO-Crate) and by HDR UK for Trusted Research Environments (Five Safes RO-Crate). Implemented by Galaxy for data and workflows and Nextflow. Used in a wide variety</p>

	<p>of consortia including EuroScienceGateway, EOSC4Cancer, EOSC ENTRUST, BioIndustry4.0, BioDT, Biodiversity Genomics Europe, Helmholtz , NFDI, EU projects and USA (Jackson Labs, Brookhaven). FAIR-IMPACT call has 15 projects funded to adopted RO-Crate+FSP including RSpace and DataVerse. Other GREIs are planning adoption. NZ developed Live publications using next RO-Crates https://livepublication.github.io/LP_Pub_LID/</p>
<i>Owner</i>	<p>Main development lead by University of Manchester (ELIXIR UK) and CRS4 (BBMRI). Benefits from a large open community</p>
<i>Access/Link</i>	<p>https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/</p>

COVID-19 Disease Map

<i>Branding</i>	
<i>Short description</i>	<p>The COVID-19 Disease Map is a graphical, interactive representation of disease-relevant molecular mechanisms linking many knowledge sources. Notably, it is a computational resource for graph-based analyses and disease modelling. The diagrams of the C19DMap, curated from the literature, are integrated with relevant interaction and text mining databases.</p>
<i>Target Group</i>	<p>Researchers, Clinical researchers, Drug developers</p>
<i>Added value</i>	<p>While the Covid-19 Disease map already contained curated data from various experimental modalities and resources, the BY-COVID project has allowed development of plugins for additional resources, like bioactivity data, imaging data and structural data, making it richer in information content and attractive for researchers from different domains.</p>
<i>Type of result</i>	<p>SERV (Service improved)</p>
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	<p>COVID-19 Disease Map diagrams are browsable via WikiPathways, Reactome, the MINERVA Platform. The workflows, executable models and network models are available via: the GitLab repository (https://gitlab.lcsb.uni.lu/covid/models), FAIRDOMHub(https://fairdomhub.org/projects/190) (based on FAIRDOM-SEEK). The plugins are available on open access GitLab repositories (https://gitlab.lcsb.uni.lu/minerva/plugins)</p>
<i>Owner</i>	<p>Hosted by University of Luxembourg / ELIXIR Luxembourg, constructed and managed by a community of researchers. FAIRDOMHub hosted by HITS (ELIXIR-DE).</p>

Access/Link

Covid-19 Disease Map:

<https://covid19map.elixir-luxembourg.org/minerva/> . Plugins

developed for BY-COVID:

- BY-COVID EMPIAR (Aastha Mathur, Isabel Kemmer, Phil Gribbon from WP2)
- BY-COVID BioImage Archive (Aastha Mathur, Isabel Kemmer, Phil Gribbon from WP2)
- (in preparation) BY-COVID Single Cell RNASeq on Galaxy (Andrew Stubbs, Helena Rasche, Iacopo Cristoferi)

BY-COVID Citizen Engagement Material

<i>Branding</i>	
<i>Short description</i>	A selection of illustrated examples for engaging citizens in open science concepts in infectious disease research, also compiled into a booklet (in 5 languages) with ideas for teachers of young people aged 14-19+
<i>Target Group</i>	Citizens, Education/training organization/learners
<i>Added value</i>	Engaged and knowledgeable citizens, builds trust and enables informed consent decisions for data sharing.
<i>Type of result</i>	PO – Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	Extensive dissemination of school booklet in 5 languages (e.g. social media, submission to educational resource platforms). Exploitation (e.g. creation of impact through engaged citizens) likely through third parties (ie educators).
<i>Owner</i>	ELIXIR External Relations Team
<i>Access/Link</i>	https://by-covid.org/usecases

BY-COVID Training Materials

<i>Branding</i>	
<i>Short description</i>	a collection of training materials generated during the BY-COVID project. These outcomes take the form of online or in-person events to bring together experts of BY-COVID and beyond to: demonstrate best practices, exchange experiences, produce content for the IDTK and training, provide training and build capacity.
<i>Target Group</i>	Researchers, data producers, data providers, etc
<i>Added value</i>	Unique set of materials that others can learn from.
<i>Type of result</i>	EVNT – Event (conference, seminar, workshop) PROD – Product (new or improved)
<i>Steps undertaken towards exploitation</i>	The training materials developed during the project were annotated with basic metadata following the Bioschemas Training profiles, and the metadata was included in the BY-COVID website. The webpage is scrapped by TeSS, the ELIXIR Training platform, and may be scrapped by other Research Infrastructure portals. These materials can now more easily be seen by search engines and embedded in other websites. Most of the steps to make these materials Open and FAIR were thus taken during the project.
<i>Owner</i>	WP1-5 (all those who have provided training)
<i>Access/Link</i>	https://by-covid.org/resources

